

Unusual patterns found in prime numbers that hints primes are not arbitrary distributed

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Abstract

Prime numbers are very special numbers, and a lot of research has been made to find patterns in primes. In this paper, the author tries to find a hidden pattern never discovered before.

This paper uses a simple algorithm written in JavaScript to automate the calculations with the intent to find more prime numbers based on one prime number. However, with further testing, listing the results, and one unintentional mistake in code, patterns were found. Furthermore, possibly more patterns can be found. What makes these results interesting is the results are not based on the characteristics of prime numbers themselves. However, it is based on finding the next prime numbers, the backward relation of the next prime numbers to the previous ones, and how many can one prime number find the next primes. The code can be found in GitHub [repo](#)[1]

Introduction

Are prime numbers really random or have some strict patterns they follow? This question is still an unanswered question, Moreover, it has the most mysterious non-obvious answer.

In this paper, based on the simple algorithm, the author tries to find patterns in the results of the list of data by finding hidden patterns never found before. Additionally, the author offers other prime numbers lovers to try to find other patterns with more creative tools and equations.

Properties of prime numbers

Prime numbers are defined by whole numbers greater than 1 that are only divisible by 1 and themselves.

This means $\forall a, b, p \in \mathbb{N}, p = a + b, \gcd(a, b) = 1$ where p is a prime number

From that property, the algorithm intended to search for equation 1:

$p^2 = (a \cdot b) + 1, b = p - (p \div 2), a = p - b, a \oplus b \text{ are prime}$. However, what has been calculated with the same condition $p = a + b$ where $a \oplus p$ are primes of the equation

$p^2 = (a \cdot c) + 1$ where $c = p \div 2$ where c is the result of the euclidean division of p by 2

Furthermore another property $p = a + b$, where a, b are primes

Algorithm

Full html page

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">

<head>
  <meta charset="UTF-8">
  <meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
  <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
  <title>Document</title>
</head>

<body>
  <table border="1">
    <tr>
      <th>number</th>
      <th>one number is prime</th>
      <th>both two numbers are primes</th>
      <th>isPrime</th>
    </tr>
    <tbody id="numberTrue"></tbody>
  </table>

  <script>
    function isPrime(num) {
      for (var i = 2; i < num; i++)
        if (num % i === 0) return false;
      return num > 1;
    }

    function addition(num) {
      //let num = document.getElementById("number").value;
      console.log(num)
      //if (isPrime(num)) {
      var quotient = Math.floor(num / 2);
      var remainder = num % 2;
      let falseCounter = 0;
      let oneTrue = 0;
      let twoTrue = 0;
      let secondmult = 0;
      let thirdmult = 0
      let noPrime = 0
      for (let index = 2; index <= quotient; index++) {
```

```

        if (isPrime(index) && (isPrime(num - index))) {
            twoTrue += 1
            if (isPrime((index * quotient) + 1)) {
                thirdmult++
            }
        } else if (isPrime(index) ^ (isPrime(num - index))) {
            oneTrue += 1
            if (isPrime((index * quotient) + 1)) {
                secondmult++
                console.log(index + " * " + quotient + " = " + ((index *
quotient) + 1))
            }
        }
    }

    return [secondmult, thirdmult];
}
//}
for (let p = 2; p <= 1000; p++) {
    let result = addition(p);
    let color = ""
    let background = ""
    if (isPrime(p)) {
        color = "white";
        background = "black"
    }
    document.getElementById("numberTrue").innerHTML += "<tr><td
style='color:" + color + ";background-color:" + background + "'>"
        + p + "</td><td>"
        + result[0]
        + "</td><td>" + result[1] +
        "</td><td>" + isPrime(p) +
        "</td></tr>";
}

</script>
</body>

</html>

```

Patterns

The first column is for the number, if the number is prime then background color of that number is black otherwise is white.

The second column is for the condition $p = a + b$ where $a \oplus p$ are primes one number either a or b must be prime, and it counts how many prime numbers the equation has

$$p^2 = (a \cdot c) + 1, b = p - (p \div 2), a = p - b, a \oplus b \text{ are prime where } c = p \div 2$$

The third column is for both a,b are primes, and it counts how many prime numbers it found.

The fourth column is boolean for checking if the number is prime or not.

number	one number is prime	both two numbers are primes	isPrime
2	0	0	true
3	0	0	true
4	0	1	false
5	0	1	true
6	1	0	false
7	0	1	true
8	0	1	false
9	2	0	false
10	1	0	false
11	1	0	true
12	2	1	false
13	3	1	true
14	0	0	false
15	1	0	false
16	1	1	false
17	2	0	true

Figure 1: example 1 of the table

Figure 2: example of output with console output that calculate and show if the number multiplied is a prime number

Pattern 1

Pattern 1: for the continues composed numbers which do not get interfered with prime numbers based on the equation, $p = a + b$, where a, b are primes most of the time there is a gap by 3 as shown in figure 3

140	6	6	false
141	11	0	false
142	0	0	false
143	4	0	false
144	3	3	false
145	12	0	false
146	0	0	false
147	2	0	false
148	7	1	false

Figure 3: pattern 1: gap between finding next prime numbers

920	22	8	false
921	30	0	false
922	0	0	false
923	12	0	false
924	16	12	false
925	47	0	false
926	0	0	false
927	11	0	false
928	24	2	false

Figure 4: pattern 1 example 2

Pattern 2

for the continues composed numbers which do not get interfered with prime numbers based on the equation $p^2 = (a \cdot c) + 1$ where $c = p \div 2$ with the condition $p = a + b$, where a, b are primes also most of the time there is a gap by 3 by when the equation find next prime numbers

954	0	0	false
955	14	0	false
956	20	3	false
957	19	0	false
958	0	0	false
959	9	0	false
960	22	20	false
961	57	0	false
962	0	0	false
963	9	0	false
964	23	3	false
965	22	0	false

Figure 5: pattern 2: example 1

890	0	0	false
891	14	0	false
892	14	4	false
893	16	0	false
894	0	0	false
895	13	0	false
896	18	5	false
897	27	0	false
898	0	0	false
899	8	0	false
900	18	7	false
901	46	0	false
902	0	0	false
903	11	0	false
904	20	4	false
905	23	0	false

Figure 6: pattern 2: example 2

Pattern 3

When interfere with the prime number, the number right before the non-twin prime number will refer to that prime number. If the second column only refer to the next prime number it will act like 0 and continue pattern #2

914	0	0	false
915	8	0	false
916	22	4	false
917	20	0	false
918	1	0	false
919	19	0	true
920	22	8	false
921	30	0	false
922	0	0	false

Figure 7: pattern 3 : example 1

942	0	0	false
943	15	0	false
944	22	3	false
945	21	0	false
946	1	0	false
947	12	0	true
948	31	6	false
949	55	0	false
950	0	0	false

Figure 8: pattern 3: example 2

Pattern 4

When it interferes with the prime number. If the number right before the non-twin prime number will not only refer to the next prime number but more prime numbers. If the second column refers to more next prime number, pattern #2 is applied, ignoring the prime number. Furthermore, the prime number is usually in the last position right before the 0.

290	0	0	false
291	7	0	false
292	10	4	false
293	12	0	true
294	0	0	false
295	11	0	false
296	11	0	false
297	6	0	false
298	0	0	false
299	5	0	false
300	9	10	false
301	27	0	false
302	0	0	false

Figure 9: pattern 4 example 1

370	0	0	false
371	9	0	false
372	16	1	false
373	22	0	true
374	0	0	false
375	7	0	false

Figure 10: pattern 4 example 2

Pattern 5

the second column usually have ascendant numbers there is many exceptions though.

574	0	0	false
575	8	0	false
576	19	5	false
577	27	0	true
578	0	0	false
579	8	0	false
580	12	6	false
581	19	0	false
582	0	0	false

Figure 11: pattern 5 example 1

Pattern 6

In the third column if the number inside is not zero then number is always in the middle of the second column, and in the second column if the number is not zero than he is in the row of the middle third column

662	0	0	false
663	8	0	false
664	12	3	false
665	15	0	false
666	0	0	false
667	15	0	false
668	16	2	false
669	16	0	false
670	0	0	false
671	7	0	false
672	15	8	false

Figure 12: pattern 6 example 1

676	20	2	false
677	15	0	true
678	0	0	false
679	10	0	false
680	13	9	false
681	23	0	false
682	1	0	false

Figure 13: pattern 6 example 2

Pattern 7

If there are twin numbers it will interfere the previous pattern as shown in the figures

806	0	0	false
807	8	0	false
808	19	2	false
809	22	0	true
810	1	0	false
811	18	1	true
812	17	4	false
813	17	0	false
814	0	0	false
815	7	0	false
816	23	6	false
817	37	0	false
818	0	0	false
819	9	0	false
820	22	8	false
821	31	0	true
822	1	0	false
823	21	1	true
824	16	4	false
825	15	0	false

Figure 14: pattern 7 example 1

850	0	0	false
851	12	0	false
852	30	5	false
853	40	0	true
854	0	0	false
855	11	0	false
856	17	7	false
857	20	0	true
858	1	0	false
859	21	1	true
860	28	8	false
861	25	0	false
862	1	0	false
863	11	0	true
864	19	9	false

Figure 15: pattern 7 example 2

Conclusion

All this requires us to further research patterns in prime numbers, taking into notice that these paper results are limited for the first 1000 number, the limitation is caused by limited hardware for computing. Moreover, the algorithm needs more optimization and finding more creative equations to find more patterns.

We come to the conclusion that maybe the prime numbers are not random after all.

Links

[1]<https://github.com/maher1719/patterns-in-prime-number>